

Syntheses of 2-Substituted Indole Derivatives through Fischer-Indole Method

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Indole Compounds have been prepared with good yields using Fischer syntheses in three different methods.

A number of general methods for the syntheses of indole derivatives have been reported¹. Among these, the well-known FISCHER synthesis² proved to be the most versatile for the synthesis of indole compounds. In the present investigation new 2-substituted indoles have been prepared in a good yield by the condensation of phenylhydrazine with a variety of methylketones (Table I). During the preparation of these indoles it was found that the use of an inert solvent such as naphthalene resulted in an improved yield³. The reaction has also been carried out in glacial acetic acid⁴ and boron trifluoride etherate⁵ as condensation agents. The general equation is as follows :

TABLE I

Comp.	Ketones used	R	M.p. of product °C	Yield % for methods		
				A	B	C
I	2-acetylnaphthalene	2-naphthyl	163	75	70	80
II	2-acetylfluorene	2-fluoryl	180	73	70	75
III	4-acetylbiphenyl	4-biphenyl	167	76	73	82
IV	5-acetylidane	5-indyle	127	40	45	50
V	3-acetylidole	3-indole	190	45	40	55
VI	2-acetylpyridine	2-pyridyl	153	65	74	82
VII	3-acetylpyridine	3-pyridyl	133	65	70	80
VIII	4-acetylpyridine	4-pyridyl	241	68	62	75

1. W. C. Sumpter and F. M. Miller. *The Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds*, 1933, **1**, 606.
2. E. Fischer and K. Jourdan, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 2241; E. Fischer and R. Hess, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 559.
3. W. H. Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 1825.
4. H. R. Snyder, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 2452.
5. C. Pauling and K. Sherman, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1933, **1**, 606.

In the case of 5-acetylidane and 3-acetylidole, a lower yield was observed, while, in the other ketones, a higher yield was obtained. It was further noted that continuous heating caused an increase in the yield of the product.

A summary of the analytical and UV data are listed in Table II (Indole λ 238, 290 and 2-methyl indole λ 235, 292).

TABLE II

Comp.	Formula	C%		H%		N%		λ Maximum	log E
		calc.	found	calc.	found	calc.	found		
I	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N	88.86	88.63	5.39	5.46	5.76	5.70	245; 305	4.75; 4.65
II	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N	89.65	89.75	5.37	5.50	4.98	5.05	247; 308	4.65; 4.55
III	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N	89.18	89.30	5.61	5.55	5.20	5.25	242; 295	4.45; 4.40
IV	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N	87.51	87.35	6.48	6.60	6.00	5.96	240; 295	4.50; 4.45
V	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂	82.73	82.78	5.21	5.25	12.06	12.20	250; 298	4.65; 4.50
VI	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂	80.38	80.45	5.19	5.23	14.42	14.55	255; 305	4.75; 4.60
VII	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂	80.38	80.47	5.19	5.25	14.42	14.45	253; 300	4.65; 4.50
VIII	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂	80.38	80.33	5.19	5.15	14.42	14.36	250; 305	4.60; 4.40

EXPERIMENTAL

Method (a): A mixture of the phenylhydrazone (1 part) and naphthalene (5 parts) was kept under continuous reflux for 4 hr. The condensation product was cooled and petroleum (b.p. 40–60°) was added to remove the naphthalene. The residue was filtered, washed repeatedly with cold alcohol, and dried. Recrystallization from benzene or hot ethanol resulted in the formation of the pure compound.

Method (b): A mixture of phenylhydrazine (1 mole) and the ketone (1 mole) was refluxed in acetic acid for 3–4 hr. On cooling, the product started to separate. It was filtered, washed with water and left to dry. Recrystallization from benzene or ethanol furnished the pure indole derivative.

Method (c): A mixture of phenylhydrazone derivative (1 part) and BF₃—etherate (2 parts) in acetic acid were refluxed for 1 hr., poured into excess water and the aqueous suspension was extracted with ether and washed with K₂CO₃ solution. Removal of the ether, and crystallization of the residue from benzene or ethanol, furnished the pure product.

All m.p.s. are uncorrected and were measured on a kofler hot bench (Mikro 610e), Riechert, Wein instrument. Microanalyses were carried out by Alfred Bernhardt's Max-Plank-Inst., Ruhr, West Germany.